
The VPS35-D620N mutation is associated with Parkinson's disease and can be a target for gene therapy

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Abstract: There is evidence that the VPS35 protein impacts degradation of dopaminergic (DA) neuron lifespan and that the D620N mutation is associated with a kind of Parkinson's disease (PD) mimicking idiopathic PD. The incidence of this mutation and the likely pathogenic effects of additional VPS35 variants is unclear. Other unusual VPS35 mutations may put people at risk for Parkinson's disease, but the level of risk has yet to be determined. Due to the functional and genetic links between VPS35 and other PD-associated genes, rare VPS35 variants may be a key extra component in developing the PD phenotype in people with other mutations with inadequate penetration. Genetic association analysis could remedy this issue in the near future.

VPS35-associated PD neuropathology is another significant aspect. Since just one D620N mutant carrier has been studied at autopsy to date, limited information is available about the neuropathological spectrum of PD patients with VPS35 mutations. It is yet unknown if neuronal loss in VPS35-related PD occurs just in SNc or affects other brain areas such as locus coeruleus, cortex, hippocampus and other structures. Neuropathology of VPS35-D620N mice models demonstrated severe tau pathology and axonal degradation, but no evidence of SYN inclusions. It's uncertain if PD individuals with VPS35 mutations have the same features.

More study on the role of VPS35 in enhancing DA neuron survival is also needed to better understand the metabolic pathways damaged by VPS35 mutations and identify new therapy goals. The D620N VPS35 KI model, paired with the parkinQ311X mouse model, is one of the first monogenic PD models to recapitulate the fundamental PD feature: DA neuronal breakdown in SNc. These mouse models can be used to identify and assess drug targets. Because the neurodegenerative molecular pathways in many types of Parkinson's disease are so similar, drugs that confer neuroprotection in VPS35 models could be studied in other, more common types of Parkinson's disease.

1. Introduction

Parkinson's disease (PD) is a neurological condition characterized by bradykinesia, rest tremor, stiffness, and gait abnormalities (Obeso et al. 2017). The increasing malfunction and degradation of dopaminergic (DA) neurons in the substantia nigra pars compacta (SNc), as well as the loss of DA inputs to the striatum, causes these motor symptoms. Other peripheral and central neural pathways and transmitter systems (serotonin, noradrenaline, and acetylcholine) are also impacted in PD, but to varied degrees, according to post-mortem investigations (Dickson et al. 2009; Schapira et al. 2017). This explains a wide range of non-

motor symptoms in Parkinson's disease, including neuropsychiatric symptoms, autonomic dysfunction, and sleep and wakefulness abnormalities (Pont-Sunyer et al. 2015).

Most cases of PD have a multifactorial aetiology, with harmful environmental and genetic factors likely to blame (Borrageiro et al. 2018; Marras et al. 2019; Pang et al. 2019), but in a small percentage of cases (5 to 10%), the disease is caused by well-defined mutations in genes that cause the autosomal dominant or recessive form of PD (Borrageiro et al. 2018; Marras (Deng et al. 2018; Lunati et al. 2018). The VPS35 gene (Vilario-Güell et al. 2011; Zimprich et al. 2011; Chen et al. 2017) has recently been identified as a cause of late-onset familial PD (Vilario-Güell et al. 2011; Chen et al. 2017). Although rare, mutations in the VPS35 gene have been linked to the development of Parkinson's disease (Klein et al. 2018). Pathogenic pathways important to the disease's development have been discovered from studies of the gene's protein products. These findings add to our understanding of the pathogenic processes behind this unusual type of PD, as well as the processes of DA neuronal malfunction, degeneration, and survival in other, more common forms of the disease.

2. Structure and Localization of VPS35

A study looking into the genes involved in the construction of lysosome-like vacuoles and the sorting of vacuolar proteins discovered the VPS35 gene in *Saccharomyces cerevisiae* (Paravicini et al. 1992). Vps35p is the name of a recently discovered yeast gene that codes for a 936-amino-acid protein. The researchers discovered that while Vps35p mutant yeast cells had morphologically normal vacuoles, they had serious problems with carboxypeptidase Y, a soluble vacuolar hydrolase. These findings suggested that VPS35 mutant cells were capable of vacuole construction and that the VPS35 protein was required for sorting a subset of vacuolar proteins. Vps35p forms a multimeric complex with four additional peripheral membrane proteins (Vps29p, Vps26p, Vps5p, and Vps17p) that localize to the cytosolic face of the prevacuolar compartment and vesicles, according to subcellular fractionation experiments. The retromer complex was called after experimental results that revealed it plays a major role in retrograde transport from the endosome to the Golgi (Seaman et al. 1998).

Vps35p is highly similar to a protein present in the human genome, according to BLAST searches comparing its sequences to those in the GenBank database and a database of human expressed sequence tags (ESTs) (Seaman et al. 1997). The human Vps35p homologue (hVPS35) is a 796-residue protein that is encoded by a gene on chromosome 16. hVPS35 is virtually universally expressed in human tissues, according to expression analyses. The brain, heart, testis, ovary, small intestine, spleen, skeletal muscle, and placenta have greater levels of expression, whereas the pancreas, thymus, prostate, and colon have moderate levels, and the lung, liver, kidney, and peripheral blood leukocytes have lower amounts (Haft et al. 2000; Zhang et al. 2000).

The *S. cerevisiae* Vps35p protein sequence was aligned with the hVPS35 protein sequence and found to have 29 percent identity and 61 percent similarity (Edgar and Polak 2000). hVPS35 shared 99.4% similarity with mouse and rat protein VPS35 (Zhang et al. 2000), 92.7 percent with *Xenopus* VPS35, and 99.5–100% with non-human primates' VPS35 protein. Secondary structure predictions and sequencing analysis strongly imply that the VPS35 protein has a-helical solenoid structure with 17 HEAT-like helical repeats (a total of 34-helices) (Hierro et al. 2007). In mammalian cells, hVPS35 forms a 150-kDa 1:1:1 heterotrimer with two additional peripheral membrane proteins (VPS26 and VPS29) to form the core of the mammalian retromer complex, much as it does in yeast (Hierro et al. 2007).

Vps35, at its N-terminus, and Vps29, at its C-terminus, comprise the core platform for binding Vps26 and Vps29 (Luet al. 2016). The core of the mammalian retromer complex interacts with a variety of membrane-associated and cytosolic proteins, according to X-ray crystallography, small-angle X-ray scattering, biochemistry, and biological studies. Key retromer partners (SNX6) include sorting nexin-1 (SNX1), sorting nexin-2 (SNX2), sorting nexin-5 (SNX5), and sorting nexin-6 (SNX6). Human homologues of Vps5p and Vps17p are SNX1/SNX2 and SNX5/SNX6, respectively. Phospholipid-binding domains (PX domain phospho homology (PX) and bin/amphiphysin/rvs (BAR) domains) distinguish these proteins (Teasdale and Collins 2012). Through interactions with a variety of accessory proteins, retromer regulates membrane recruitment, cargo selection, and retromer trafficking. Retromer complexes are typically found in endosomal compartments. Rab5 and Rab7, two small GTPases that work together to control the connection with endosomes, are involved in its recruitment to endosomes (Rojas et al. 2008; Seaman et al. 2009). Rab7 interacts directly with Vps35's N-terminal conserved areas, and Rab7's interaction with Vps35 is required for core retromer complex endosomal recruitment (Priya et al. 2015). The retromer complex core forms a coat on membrane tubules with accessory proteins and governs the cellular localization (retrograde transport to the TGN and recycling to the plasma membrane) of hundreds of transmembrane proteins in various tissues. Classic retromer payloads such as the cation-independent mannose 6-phosphate receptor (CI-MPR) and the α -2 adrenergic receptor (B2AR) are trafficked to diverse cellular sites. B2AR is recycled from internal membranes to the plasma membrane, whereas CI-MPR is transported from the endosome to Golgi (Temkin et al. 2011; Varandas et al. 2016).

Many other retromer cargoes have been discovered, including the triggering receptor expressed on myeloid cells 2 (TREM2), an immunomodulatory receptor expressed preferentially in the microglia of the central nervous system (Yin et al. 2016), the parathyroid hormone receptor PTH1R, a G protein-coupled receptor expressed in osteoblasts (Sims 2016), and many others (Seaman 2012; Li et al. 2016).

While several retromer payloads have been found in a variety of cellular types, the specific role of the retromer in tissues is still partially understood. Because of its widespread expression, it is likely to play an important role in the formation and maintenance of many cell types in the CNS and peripheral organs. Retromer's significance in adipogenesis and pathogen proliferation in tissues, for example, has just lately been found (Yang et al. 2016; Elwell and Engel 2018). The homozygous deletion of VPS35 in mice causes early embryonic mortality (Wen et al. 2011), highlighting the relevance of VPS35 and the retromer complex in the development and homeostasis of numerous organs.

VPS35 Mutations in Parkinson's Disease Patients

A missense mutation in the VPS35 gene was described as a cause of late-onset PD in two separate investigations published in 2011 (Vilario-Güell et al. 2011; Zimprich et al. 2011). The authors discovered the heterozygous mutation c.18589G > A (p.Asp620Asn) in all afflicted family members and a few unaffected individuals using whole exome sequencing (WES) technology, indicating that the condition is autosomal dominant with incomplete penetrance. Following this, screening of all 17 exons of the VPS35 gene in different PD families identified six more missense variations with unknown significance (Vilario-Güell et al. 2011; Zimprich et al. 2011; Chen et al. 2017). The p.Asp620Asn mutation has been found in patients with sporadic or familial PD in five investigations thus far. Other genetic studies involving PD patient cohorts from various countries suggest that VPS35 mutations are not a

common cause of familial PD (Verstraeten et al. 2012; Zhang et al. 2012; Deng et al. 2012; Guella et al. 2012; Guo et al. 2012; Nuytemans et al. 2012; Chen et al. 2012); however, since other genetic studies involving PD patient cohorts from In addition to the p.Asp620Asn mutation, 13 other missense variants in the VPS35 gene have been identified in at least one patient with Parkinson's disease (Vilario-Güell et al. 2011; Zimprich et al. 2011; Ando et al. 2012; Sharma et al. 2012; Verstraeten et al. 2012; Nuytemans et al. 2013), but their pathological significance is unknown The motor and non-motor aspects in individuals with mutant VPS35 are indistinguishable from idiopathic PD in terms of clinical parameters. In certain situations, the age of onset is sooner than in idiopathic PD. Wider et al. 2008; Zimprich et al. 2011; Vilario-Güell et al. 2011; Ando et al. 2012; Kumar et al. 2012; Sharma et al. 2012; Sheerin et al. 2012; Verstraeten et al. 2012; Nuytemans et al. 2013; Gorostidi et al. 2016; Chen et al. 2017) have described the clinical In summary, VPS35 gene mutations appear to be an uncommon cause of Parkinson's disease, and the pathogenicity of the p.Asp620Asn mutation seems definite. Other variations' pathogenicity and possible impact on neurodegeneration will need to be determined through functional research.

In both mouse and human models, VPS35 causes dopaminergic neuron degeneration.

This paradigm can not be utilized to explore the neurodegeneration associated with a loss of VPS35 function since animals knockout for VPS35 die early during embryonic development (Wen et al. 2011). Tsika et al. used a viral model of VPS35-associated PD to investigate the pathogenic implications of VPS35 mutations in vivo. By stereotactic injection, adeno-associated viral vectors expressing hVPS35, WT, or D620N were delivered to the substantia nigra of adult rats. D620N VPS35 expression resulted in a 32 percent loss of SNc DA neurons, while WT VPS35 expression resulted in a 25 percent loss of DA neurons. These findings, according to the scientists, indicate a gain-of-function mechanism for the D620N mutation (Tsika et al. 2014).

Tang et al. developed two mouse models, one with a VPS35 heterozygote (VPS35^{+/-}) and the other with a VPS35 gene deletion in DA neurons (VPS35DAT-Cre) (Tang et al. 2015b). The VPS35^{+/-} animals lived to adulthood, but they had a 20% loss of DA neurons in the SNc and an accumulation of-synuclein (SYN) at 12 months. The VPS35DAT-Cre animals demonstrated a significant drop in DA neurons in the SNc, a drop in DA fibres in the striatum, and elevated SYN levels in the SNc at 2 months of age. VPS35-haploinsufficiency in DA neurons, according to the investigators, enhances PD development (Tang et al. 2015b). VPS35 knock-in (KI) mice with the D620N mutation were created and described in three investigations (Ishizu et al. 2016; Cataldi et al. 2018; Chen et al. 2019). Even at 70 weeks of age, Ishizu et al. discovered a reduction in evoked striatal DA release in homozygous VPS35-D620N KI mice, but no obvious neurodegeneration in homozygous and heterozygous VPS35-D620N KI animals (Ishizu et al. 2016). Cataldi et al. looked at an independent VPS35-D620N KI model and found no neurodegeneration in mice at 3 months of age (21 weeks), as measured by DA neuron count in the SNc and analyses of TH expression in the striatum (Cataldi et al. 2018); however, they did find changes in the levels of synaptic markers like dopamine transporter (DAT) and vesicular monoamine transporter 2 ((VMAT2). This result revealed that the dopaminergic system of VPS35 D620N KI mice had early synaptic impairment (Cataldi et al. 2018). The VPS35-D620N KI model was further defined in another investigation (Chen et al. 2019). Scientists discovered that D620N VPS35 expression had a minor influence on motor performance even at advanced age; nevertheless, at 13 months of age, both homozygous and heterozygous VPS35-D620N mice showed a considerable loss of DA neurons when compared to WT mice (Chen et al. 2019). This

discrepancy shows that a heterozygous or homozygous D620N mutation is enough to cause progressive nigrostriatal pathway degradation in a mouse model. VPS35's involvement in controlling DA neuron survival was also verified by the model. The reasons for the discrepancy when compared to Ishizu et al.'s model (Ishizu et al. 2016) are unknown.

Induced pluripotent stem cells (iPSCs) were created from fibroblasts of VPS35 PD patients with the p.D620N mutation to create human models. The DA neurons were acquired following differentiation and compared to control participants' DA neurons (Munsie et al. 2015). The D620N neurons contained higher amounts of the AMPAR subunit GluA1, indicating faulty AMPAR trafficking (Munsie et al. 2015); However, no information concerning the survival of these DA neurons was provided. Future research on iPSC-derived human DA neurons is needed to see if this in vitro model can mimic in vivo degeneration.

3. VPS35 Influences Cellular Organelle Function

VPS35's Role in the Retromer Complex as a Lysosome Function Regulator

The degradative end sites for both internal and external cargo are lysosomes (and their yeast equivalents, vacuoles). Many proteases, lipases, nucleases, and other hydrolytic enzymes perform their catabolic function by breaking complicated macromolecules down into their basic building blocks (Lawrence and Zoncu 2019). The CI-MPR is responsible for sorting lysosomal hydrolase precursors from the trans-Golgi network (TGN) to pre-lysosomal compartment network endosomes in mammals. CI-MPR transports acid hydrolase precursors from the TGN to endosomes, where they are delivered to the lysosomes. The unoccupied receptors must return to the TGN for additional sorting after releasing the hydrolase precursors into the endosomal lumen. This retrieval mechanism includes the mammalian retromer complex (Bonifacino and Hurley 2008). In specifically, the hVPS35 subunit of retromer interacts with the cytosolic domain of the CI-MPR in an endosomal compartment and sequesters the CI-MPR into recycling tubules, limiting their transportation to vacuoles or lysosomes (Arighi et al. 2004; Seaman 2005).

In human cells, RNA interference inhibits acid hydrolase receptors from being retrieved to the TGN, causing them to missort to the vacuole or lysosomes, where they are destroyed. This method causes lysosomes to enlarge by increasing CI-MPR lysosomal turnover, decreasing cellular levels of lysosomal hydrolases, and increasing lysosomal turnover (Arighi et al. 2004; Seaman 2005). Further research revealed that VPS35-deficient DA neurons or DA neurons harboring the PD-linked VPS35 mutant D620N exhibited poor endosome-to-Golgi retrieval of Lamp2a and accelerated Lamp2a degradation (Tang et al. 2015a). Lamp2a is a chaperone-mediated autophagy receptor that is required for SYN degradation (Mak et al. 2010; Xilouri et al. 2013). The researchers discovered a substantial decrease in Lamp2a in the ventral midbrain of VPS35 and VPS35-D620N mice, but not in the striatum or hippocampus, as well as a temporal and brain-regional relationship between Lamp2a reduction and SYN rise. Lamp2a expression was also shown to lower SYN levels in VPS35-deficient DA neurons, indicating that Lamp2a is a chaperone-mediated autophagy receptor important for SYN breakdown. As a consequence, these findings imply that, in addition to CI-MPR, Lamp2a is another cargo of VPS35/retromer in DA neurons, and that this route, VPS35-Lamp2a-SYN, is important in preventing PD development (Tang et al. 2015a).

According to a recent study, VPS35 regulates iron trafficking across the Golgi network by altering the subcellular distribution of labile Fe (ii), which is defined as a protein-free or weakly protein-bound form of Fe (ii) ions capable of causing oxidative damage via Fenton

chemistry (Enami et al. 2014). Knocking down hVPS35 in SH-SY5Y neuroblastoma cells reduced the baseline level of labile Fe (ii) in the Golgi and caused lysosomal accumulation of labile Fe (ii). In addition, lysosomal accumulation of divalent metal transporter 1, a protein that functions as a main transporter of Fe (ii) ions, was increased by hVPS35 knockdown (Hirayama et al. 2019). The SH-SY5Y harboring the mutant variant VPS35-D620N also accumulated divalent metal transporter 1. (Kumar et al. 2012; Mohan and Mellick 2017).

Autophagy, a degradative system in which the breakdown of cellular proteins releases the amino acids required for life, is likely to be disrupted by PD-causing mutations in VPS35, especially under famine or stress circumstances (Kroemer et al. 2010). Birmingham et al. (2006) found that autophagy eliminates damaged mitochondria and intracellular pathogens, as well as facilitates the clearance of intracytoplasmic aggregate-prone proteins (Ravikumar 2002; Webb et al. 2003; Ravikumar et al. 2004). The PD-associated mutation VPS35-D620N lowered the endosomal recruitment of the protein complex called Wiskott–Aldrich Syndrome Protein and SCAR Homolog, according to Zavodszky et al (WASH). This is an actin-regulating complex made up of five proteins (FAM21, WASH1, strumpellin, CCDC53, and KIAA1033) that interacts with the retromer complex to attract it to endosomes and play a role in endosomal sorting. VPS35 D620N has a lower affinity for WASH complex proteins, which destabilizes the retromer–WASH complex interaction (McGough et al. 2014) and leads to decreased WASH complex endosomal localization. Because WASH complex binding to retromer is required for autophagy, disrupting WASH complex binding causes autophagy to be disrupted (Zavodszky et al. 2014).

To summarize, loss of VPS35 function or expression of mutant VPS35 D620N inhibits autophagy and has a significant influence on lysosome function. These pathways are very likely to have a role in neuronal death.

VPS35's Role in Mitochondrial Function

VPS35 was discovered on mitochondrial-derived vesicles (MDVs), which convey cargo from the mitochondria to the peroxisomes (Neuspiel et al. 2008). VPS35 was discovered in a complex with mitochondrial-anchored protein ligase (MAPL), a small ubiquitin-like modifier (SUMO) E3 ligase that is present on MDVs. The researchers also discovered that silencing VPS35 reduces MAPL transport to peroxisomes, indicating that VPS35 and the retromer are involved in an unique intracellular trafficking pathway that leads to the production of MDVs (Braschi et al. 2010).

VPS35 also regulates mitochondrial fusion and fission, which might be another method for it to influence mitochondrial function. Tang et al. discovered that VPS35 deficiency lowers mitochondrial MFN2, a GTPase located in the outer mitochondrial membrane that is required for mitochondrial fusion, in neuronal cell lines, DA neurons, and brain tissues. VPS35-depleted DA neurons' mitochondria were shorter and rounder than control neurons' mitochondria, suggesting that VPS35 depletion causes mitochondrial fragmentation. The expression of the VPS35 wild type, but not the PD-linked mutant VPS35-D620N, reduced mitochondrial fragmentation in VPS35-depleted neurons (Tang et al. 2015b). The researchers next looked at how VPS35 may influence MFN2 protein levels and mitochondrial fusion dynamics. They discovered that VPS35 inhibits MUL1-mediated MFN2 degradation via regulating the trafficking and degradation of the E3 ubiquitin ligase MUL1 (Tang et al. 2015b). VPS35 interacts with MUL1/MAPL and is necessary for the production of MUL1/MAPL-associated MDVs, according to these findings (Braschi et al. 2010). Another research of mitochondrial morphology in in vitro and in vivo models found that VPS35

mutations in people with Parkinson's disease promote mitochondrial fragmentation. The mitochondria were labeled in cultured neurons *in vitro* using VPS35 and mitoDsRed2: overexpression of wild-type VPS35 reduced mitochondrial length and increased the percentage of neurons with fragmented mitochondria. However, when VPS35-D620N was expressed, mitochondrial fragmentation was more severe (Wang et al. 2016). The researchers also looked at mitochondrial morphology in fibroblasts from people with Parkinson's disease who had the VPS35 D620N mutation and normal human fibroblasts from age-matched healthy people. In control fibroblasts, confocal examination revealed a linked mitochondrial network, which became considerably fragmented in D620N fibroblasts. Electron microscopy also verified these results. The scientists stereotactically injected lentivirus co-expressing VPS35 (WT or mutants) and mitoDsRed2 into mouse substantia nigra and scanned the tissues 3 weeks later to investigate the effect of VPS35 mutants *in vivo*. Mitochondrial fragmentation was seen in neurons expressing WT VPS35, which became more pronounced in neurons expressing the D620N mutant. Mitochondrial fragmentation was linked to mitochondrial dysfunction in cells and tissues expressing VPS35-D620N, as measured by ATP dosage, mitochondrial membrane potential analyses, and oxygen consumption rates. The researchers looked into the relationship between VPS35 and dynamin-like protein 1 (DLP1), a GTPase that is recruited to the outer membrane of mitochondria and forms a ring-like complex to exert fission activity, and discovered that VPS35 interacts with DLP1. They hypothesized that retromer removes DLP1 complexes from mitochondria and delivers them to lysosomes for destruction via a VPS35–DLP1 interaction. The VPS35 mutation linked with PD increased the VPS35–DLP1 interaction, increased retromer-dependent turnover of the mitochondrial DLP1 complex via MDV-mediated trafficking, and shifted mitochondrial dynamics towards excessive fission, resulting in mitochondrial malfunction and neuronal death (Wang et al. 2016). In summary, growing evidence shows that VPS35 modulates mitochondrial function; future research will reveal if mitochondrial dysfunction is a significant stage in the neurodegenerative process in VPS35-mutated Parkinson's disease patients.

4. VPS35's Function in Neurotransmission

The activities of VPS35 outlined thus far (e.g., lysosomal function control and mitochondrial homeostasis) are functions that the protein may have in the tissues where it is expressed. However, because VPS35 mutations are linked to DA neuron degeneration, it's possible that the gene's mutations disrupt a specific neuronal pathway. Numerous investigations into the role of VPS35 in modifying synaptic transmission provide support to this notion.

Subcellular fractionation was used to explore the natural distribution of endogenous VPS35 in the mammalian brain. VPS35 was discovered in microsomal vesicles, crude synaptosomes, and synaptic vesicle membranes, among other vesicular compartments (Tsika et al. 2014). A closer look at the location of retromer in mouse hippocampus neuron neurites revealed that roughly 22% of VPS35 immunoreactivity was also VAMP2/synaptobrevin positivity (Vazquez-Sanchez et al. 2018). This discovery demonstrated that retromers can be found in synaptic sites and that VPS35 can regulate synapse function.

Retromer controls the trafficking of adrenergic and glutamatergic receptors to the plasma membrane (Choy et al. 2014), suggesting that VPS35 has a role at the postsynapse terminal. VPS35 loss affects dendritic spine development and lowers glutamatergic transmission, according to Tian and co-authors, who studied the function of VPS35 in neuronal spine development and maturation. They also discovered that VPS35 interacts with AMPA receptors and modulates AMPA receptor trafficking, which might explain how it promotes

spine development and glutamatergic neurotransmission (Tian et al. 2015). Another research looked at the effects of the VPS35-D620N mutation on neurons and discovered that VPS35 is located in dendritic spines and is implicated in the trafficking of excitatory AMPA-type glutamate receptors. Furthermore, VPS35-D620N is a VPS35 activity loss-of-function mutation (Munsie et al. 2015).

Vps35 is also found in presynaptic terminals near the boundary of the active zone in *Drosophila*, where it controls synaptic vesicle (SV) recycling, according to recent research. In adult brains, the capability for SV release was investigated utilizing VMAT-pHluorin in DA neurons. SV release was disrupted in neurons knocked down by Vps35 or with the Vps35-D620N mutation. These findings show that Vps35 controls SV dynamics and that Vps35 deletion in *Drosophila* influences dopamine release (Inoshita et al. 2017). Retromer is found in mammalian cells in the presynaptic terminal, according to another study. Vazquez-Sanchez et al. used electron microscopy to find positivity in a subset of hippocampus presynaptic terminals. Presynaptic immunoreactivity was discovered more frequently (82.4%) than postsynaptic immunoreactivity (17.6 percent). VPS35 depletion in hippocampal neurons, on the other hand, had no effect on presynaptic ultrastructure, SV release, or retrieval. These findings are in some ways at odds with those reported in *Drosophila* neurons (Inoshita et al. 2017). As a result, the retromer and VPS35 proteins are found at the presynaptic and postsynaptic terminals, although more research is needed to determine their functional significance.

5. VPS35 and Other Parkinson's Disease-Related Genes Could Interact

A functional connection between VPS35 and other genes linked to familial PD has been discovered in several investigations. Parkin is an E3 ubiquitin ligase encoded by the PARK2 gene that is often altered in autosomal recessive juvenile parkinsonism (ARJP). Parkin-null is a placeholder for Parkin-null, which *Drosophila* has a shorter lifespan, a faulty climbing ability, and a higher susceptibility to paraquat (Cha et al. 2005; Malik et al. 2015). VPS35 overexpression can restore parkin-mutant abnormalities in *Drosophila*, according to Malik et al (Malik et al. 2015). This study implies that VPS35 interacts with parkin on a genetic level. Furthermore, VPS35 was discovered as a parkin substrate in a research isolating ubiquitinated proteins in flies (Martinez et al. 2017). A more recent study found that parkin interacts with and ubiquitinates VPS35, demonstrating a functional relationship between the two proteins (Williams et al. 2018). Immunoprecipitation in SH-SY5Y cells co-transfected with VPS35 and parkin revealed the interaction between parkin and the retromer component VPS35. The association was not reduced by PD-associated mutations in VPS35 (D620N) or parkin (T240R, R256C, P437L, G328E, and C431F). Parkin boosted VPS35 ubiquitination in SH-SY5Y cells co-expressing HA-tagged ubiquitin, whereas family parkin mutations hindered VPS35 ubiquitination. Scientists looked into the type of ubiquitin attachment to VPS35 mediated by parkin and discovered that it is not K48-linked, which is a chain linkage that generally selects substrates for proteasomal destruction. Parkin-mediated ubiquitination of VPS35 is not a signal for its proteasomal destruction, according to scientists, and VPS35 ubiquitination may modulate retromer activity (Williams et al. 2018). Williams et al. employed adenoviral vectors to express human VPS35-D620N in the substantia nigra of parkin KO mice or WT littermates to see if parkin plays a role in the neurodegeneration produced by D620N VPS35 *in vivo*. In both WT and parkin KO mice, VPS35-D620N expression resulted in a significant loss of DA neurons. These findings show that parkin is not essential for dopaminergic neurodegeneration caused by PD-linked D620N, and that VPS35

might be downstream of parkin in a molecular route that regulates the retromer complex's activity (Williams et al. 2018).

The kinase leucine-rich repeat protein kinase-2 (LRRK2) regulates vesicular trafficking by phosphorylating a subset of Rab proteins (Rui et al. 2018). LRRK2 mutations have been associated with autosomal dominant variants of Parkinson's disease (Paisán-Ruz et al. 2004). *Drosophila* models expressing mutant versions of LRRK2 show locomotor impairments and eye lesions that are suggestive of photoreceptor loss in neural cells (Venderova et al. 2009). Linhart et al. discovered that overexpressing VPS35 completely reverses LRRK2 phenotypes. VPS35 and LRRK2 are thought to be part of the same molecular pathway, according to scientists (Linhart et al. 2014). Mir and co-authors investigated whether genetic alterations of VPS35 influenced LRRK2-mediated Rab protein phosphorylation to learn more about how VPS35 and LRRK2 interact. They discovered that knocking out VPS35 or expressing the VPS35 D620N mutant increased LRRK2 activity via increasing LRRK2 autophosphorylation. VPS35 knockdown resulted in a significant increase in LRRK2-mediated phosphorylation of numerous additional Rab proteins, which is consistent with LRRK2 activation (Mir et al. 2018).

These findings suggest that VPS35 is located upstream of LRRK2 and has a function in regulating the catalytic activity of the LRRK2 kinase.

PARK16, a non-familial PD risk-associated locus, exhibits a genetic interaction with LRRK2. RAB7L1 is one of the five genes found inside the PARK16 locus. Retromer dysfunction has been linked to LRRK2–RAB7L1 pathway abnormalities, according to MacLeod et al (MacLeod et al. 2013). Expression of the PD-variant LRRK2 G2019S or deletion of RAB7L1 resulted in a considerable decrease in VPS35 and VPS29 levels in mouse N2A neuroblastoma cells. In the mouse brain, expression of the R1441C mutant version of LRRK2 resulted in a substantial decrease in the levels of VPS35, VPS29, and VPS26. Co-immunoprecipitation investigations of LRRK2 and VPS35 revealed that the two proteins had a direct connection. Overexpression of VPS35 in *Drosophila* DA neurons prevented the loss of DA neurons induced by the PD mutation LRRK2-G2019S, and also increased the lifetime of LRRK2-G2019S mutant-expressing flies. The researchers looked at VPS35 levels in brain tissue from sporadic PD patients and unaffected people and found a substantial drop in VPS35 mRNA levels in the PD patients' tissues (MacLeod et al. 2013). These findings imply that retromer deficiency may play a role in the effect of PD-associated genetic risk variants on brain neurons.

SYN is a protein that accumulates in Parkinson's disease and other synucleinopathies (Goedert et al. 2017). Familial PD is associated with mutations in the SYN gene (SNCA) (Nussbaum 2018). The lysosome protease cathepsin D (CTSD) is involved in the breakdown of SYN (Aufschnaiter et al. 2017). VPS35 knockdown disrupted CTSD maturation in tandem with SYN accumulation in lysosomes, according to Miura et al. Furthermore, they discovered that in *Drosophila*, knocking down Vps35 caused a buildup of insoluble SYN in the brain (Miura et al. 2014). These findings imply that the retromer plays an important role in the breakdown of SYN.

Another investigation established a link between VPS35 and SYN (Dhungel et al. 2015). In a yeast model and *Caenorhabditis elegans*, the researchers discovered a genetic link between SYN and VPS35, and showed that lentiviral-mediated production of wild-type VPS35 nearly fully restored SYN-induced neurodegeneration in a mouse model. Upregulation of the PD-

linked mutant VPS35-D620N, on the other hand, resulted in more severe neuronal death. The capacity of wild-type VPS35 to diminish SYN intra-neuronal accumulation was proposed as a method by which wild-type VPS35 protected SYN mice against neurodegeneration (Dhungel et al. 2015). These data show that wild-type VPS35 inhibits SYN accumulation, but VPS35 mutant expression causes faulty SYN clearance, resulting in extensive SYN buildup. Surprisingly, more recent research showed no indication of SYN-positive neuropathology in VPS35-D620N KI mice, according to Chen and co-authors (Chen et al. 2019). They discovered that the D620N mutation, whether heterozygous or homozygous, is sufficient to recreate the main neuropathological markers of PD, such as progressive nigrostriatal pathway degradation and extensive axonal disease. Even in older VPS35 KI mice, they discovered substantial tau-positive somatodendritic pathology but no evidence of SYN positive neuropathology (Chen et al. 2019).

The cause of the disparities between these investigations is unknown. To fully understand the situation, further studies of SYN neuropathology in brain tissue from VPS35-mutated individuals' autopsies are required. So far, only one D620N mutation carrier has been identified at an autopsy. Furthermore, because no necropsy was undertaken for neuropathological evaluation, just a small amount of brain tissue was accessible from the cortex and basal ganglia, with the substantia nigra conspicuous by its absence. Immunostaining for SYN was negative in this investigation; nevertheless, the small amount of tissue analyzed prevents decisive conclusions (Wider et al. 2008).

As a result, connections between VPS35 and other PD-associated genes, such as SYNUCLEIN-PARKIN and LRRK2, may occur, implying an interplay of genes in the pathogenesis of PD that leads to synaptic, mitochondrial, and lysosomal dysfunction.

6. Conclusion

Evidence is mounting suggesting the VPS35 protein affects DA neuron survival and that the D620N mutation is linked to a type of PD that mimics idiopathic PD. The prevalence of this mutation, as well as the possible pathogenic impact of other VPS35 variations found, is unknown. Other uncommon VPS35 variations may put people at risk for Parkinson's disease, although the extent of the risk has yet to be determined (Deng et al. 2013; Williams et al. 2017). Rare VPS35 variations may be an important additional component in the development of the PD phenotype in individuals bearing other mutations with incomplete penetrance, given the functional and genetic linkages between VPS35 and other PD-associated genes. Genetic association analysis may be able to resolve this issue in the near future.

The neuropathology of VPS35-associated PD is another essential consideration. Since only one D620N mutation carrier has been evaluated at autopsy to date, little is known about the neuropathological spectrum of Parkinson's disease patients with VPS35 mutations (Wider et al. 2008). It's yet unclear if neuronal loss in VPS35-related PD happens solely in the SNc or also affects other brain regions such as the locus coeruleus, cortex, hippocampus, and other structures. The VPS35-D620N KI mice models' neuropathology revealed significant tau pathology and axonal degeneration, but no evidence of SYN inclusions (Chen et al. 2019). It's unclear whether the same characteristics are present in PD patients with VPS35 mutations. Furthermore, more research into the role of VPS35 in boosting DA neuron survival is required to better understand the biochemical pathways disrupted by VPS35 mutations and to find potential treatment targets. Importantly, combined with the parkinQ311X mouse model (Lu et al. 2009), the D620N VPS35 KI model is one of the first monogenic PD models to

mimic the essential PD feature: DA neuronal degradation in the SNc. These mouse models can be used to identify and evaluate therapeutic medication targets. Because the molecular pathways of neurodegeneration in various types of Parkinson's disease are so similar, medications that provide neuroprotection in VPS35 models may be investigated in other, more common parkinsonisms.

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